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MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATION ON THE PERIOD OF EMERGENCY VIA PANDEMIC COVID-19

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Abstract:-

E- learning in this era of pandemic has transformed our whole education system from class room trend to the modern cyber world education, thus it cannot be denied that we have somehow reached a virtual and global education system. The pandemic has promoted a new wave of interactivity with use of technology, modern digital methods in education and creating a favourable environment of education focusing on all round development of students. By its well dignified management it has also fulfilled the needs in providing education. Thus, we can undoubtedly say that by creating such informal educational environment, a revolutionary act in coming decades can be established providing many educational and technical opportunities for learners and educators.

Key Words: Management of Education, COVID-19 Pandemic

The disaster started in the end of February on sound of Covid-19, which was monitored effectively in INDIA from March 18th 2020 with the complete lock down. With the outbreak of virus, some interim measures were adopted by the Indian Government in order to regulate distance and well learning of the students, thus to overcome the negative aspect on the education of 15 million children and youth globally but unfortunately the process of education has significantly affected 1.53 billion learners out of school and across 184 country- wide schools, impacting 87.6% of the world's total enrolled learners, which is likely to rise in an unprecedented way with the spread of Covid-19. The drastic effect of this period has disrupted teaching, learning process with a long term implication of foundational learning and especially on the vulnerable children. Therefore regulating education process in this crucial time seems to be more challenging than to normal interaction (Face to Face).

What all is needed to adopt such digital method of teaching?

Which can make this state more virtual or understandable for a method of learning?

The understanding of E-Learning method by the education institution has proved the supplementary model and an open source to teach the learning management system and to bridge the loss of education in this emergency.

The digital system of Education is conducted in many ways:

- Recorded Classes.
- Live on line classes (Google-meet, Zoom etc).
- Conducting webinar by the Universities, and the use of recorded classes, which are referred to as massive open online classes (MOOC's).
- Several other platforms were also adopted in India which were supported by Ministry of Human resources development (MHRD), the National Council of Education Research and Training (NCERT), and the Department of Technical Education (DTE) for enhancement of Quality Teaching, so many another platform like online (SWAYAM) classes for students and (NEAT) online classes for teachers is also initiative under the period of Covid-19

To increase connectivity with the institution, and to accessibility to content, some national projects like National Project on Technology enhanced Learning (NPTEL) and National Knowledge Network (NKN) and National Academic Depository (NAD) are utilized.

The National Law University (NLU) Delhi was first to have an open MOOC and in March after Covid-19 emergency, it opened the course out to the public to avail the study material and digital resource of Law students as entrusted by the University Grant Commission (UGC) and Ministry of Human resource and

Development (MHRD)

G. S. Bajpai of National Law University, Delhi says- "This was a measure to cater to the needs of quality education for students across the country that are unable to join top institutions".

In the field of science and technology, such measures were also been founded in order to facilitate the students and to enhance the quality of teaching by digital teaching learning process of Education.

Thus in this period of crises, an innovation to view learning modes that can reach everyone has been globally framed by the Educational administration systematically across the globes. The pandemic had transformed the countries old and traditional method o E-teaching learning, from the technical teaching model of chalk-talk to Web Learning Method.

However, in India while technology is enabling it can also be limiting. Only private schools and institutions are mostly able to adopt the digital methods. In middle class families and people below middle class are facing a source of it and have loss of education among children. Reach and downloading of material is also sometimes impossible for the certain vigilant areas due to unfortunate climatic condition in India.

The Government and the health department (WHO) are taking preventing measures for slowing down the spread of Corona Virus Covid-19, as it has drastically affected communities globally, and has encouraged E-Learning and homeschooling to support Education System. To provide quality education, the educators and masters are doing their best in collaboration with the parents and guardians collectively. In the Nationwide programming, the lessons of all the subjects (Mathematics, English, Science, Arts, History etc) of every age of students has empowered the students to access online and distance learning solution for their success.

Quality Management by E- Learning:

By helping in their education needs, some of the countries have also

provided computers, laptops, etc to their students.

Project based learning and organizing webinars for the students has proved a new gateway into creativity for the students.

Co curricular activities like: Yoga, Art, Drawing, Painting, Home science, and many more skillful videos are downloadable, in order to enhance the comprehensiveness of the students, programs like "Road theory" "TED Ed @ Home" are playing their best role in personalized learning, reading of literature.

Another solution is "CENTURY TECH" Which had proven the best platform for winning this educational crucial situation, the change from the boundaries of the institutions to online learning at home and remote learning has been quick, drastic and unprecedented in the world of Education. Countries and organization around the world are using much innovative methods and ideas to reach the education in the remote areas by framing learning models and packaged taking into account the different needs of the students.

The fun learning method has been adopted for younger children by organizing creative games and animation for them.

E-Conferencing held between the students and the head of the institution. Our Minister's are giving proper guidance successfully as we all want our children and nation healthy.

For consistency, broadcasting education nationwide various tools of digital assessment are being implemented by the educators, like-Google-Forum, Padlets, Quizlat, Socrative, Hot potatoes, Kahoot etc.

Individual Framework:

The educators are comfortably dealing and creating an individual framework to satisfy the learners urge and clearing their doubts. To maintain the quality of education, government has also organized program so as to train our teachers digitally on E-Learnig, which has made the mode of teaching more advantageous. The teachers can

fulfill the requirement of the students and make them more compatible in this platform, Now Educational institutions that provide online degrees and professional qualifications are bound in competition to offer the most up-to-date, most affordable, most high accredited, most flexible study programs.

Time Management:

It is nevertheless to say that the Traditional method of lectures as studies show that students don't get very much out of them earlier. Even the students can practice the same method again and again by various videos which has sorted the myth of missing lectures and saved the time also. Thus, we can say that students have learned the Time management for their own individual learning. In the saved time, the students can learn other Extra Curricular Activities and make their learning more interesting and knowledgeable.

The teachers can easily identify the mistakes by getting instant feedback from online learning methods. Discussion on several topics can be easily conducted.

Providing Online Certificates:

Organization of quizzes, discussion and several competitions and games for the empowerment of making the learners more skillful is very easily and tactfully implemented by making small group of the students. The achievers are also provided with E-Certificate for their grade and participation certificate as a reward in order to foster their intense in this global competitive world of Education. This also motivates and guides others classmate and student as vigilant by their parents and guardian. The support of their family members is act as "Adding up Oil in the Lowering Lamp" or the students.

E-Learning:

E-Learning method has proved a pragmatic and innovative approach on framework Covid-19, inspite of some of its drawback, in this crucial period, the global use of technological teaching, learning have been globally introduced and has benefitted globally

all over education process especially for higher and competitive curriculum. This can also be positively notified that online tests and webinars are regulated for the quality enhancement of the learners. The evaluation system by taking online live examination has also proved the efficiency of this mode of learning. With its effective and interactive this method has proved its advancement internationally. Although, it was started since last few years, but at the time of emergency, it bridging the loss of higher education and forcing globally experimentation with remote teaching the school, universities and other educational institutions for completing their course and syllabus, are working on their remote teaching methodology and students are also acquiring the best of their knowledge from on line learning which has proved its usefulness successfully. Thus, the informal method has established such an environment in education, the can prove any revolutionary act in coming future of students and many possible technical opportunities for their forthcoming life. Thus, we hope the best of everything for aggregate knowledge and ability to get mooted and fostered by the technical system.

Crisis gives opportunity to innovate, create and activate for sustainability of human being. COVID-19 a pandemic a big crisis, it is rightly termed as "**BLACK SWAN**" event bringing unprecedented disruptions and opportunities. To the world it has given opportunity to upgrade or replace our Traditional classroom education system to the online education system. Schools schedules are more fluid and seem to depend on the teacher during pandemic. It' also been easier for teachers to get one to one or to create impromptu small group sessions. Covid-19 has impacted students across the world, as a result of the education pattern has been changed dramatically with the distinctive rise of E-Learning whereby teaching is undertaken remotely and on digital platform. Research suggests that online learning has been shown to increase retention of information, and takes less time, while countries struggling at different point of their Covid-19 period, infection rates have been increased world-wide, schools are shut and students at bay, it resulted in across the world, globally over 1.2 Billion children in 186 countries are out of classrooms as schools are closed due to pandemic. Online schools have proved that they are the need of a

modern society. During the pandemic crisis, online schools have provided continuity to education, students are responding to roll calls for their homes. Schooling pattern has been changed. The boundaries of the classroom have been breached by the teacher teachings and learners learning face to face interaction at their own homes. Covid-19 has changed education forever, as it has forced schools and teachers to change the methodology of teaching and insisted teachers to change their education pattern. In fact, students and institutions across the world have opted for online education and these mediums are embraced worldwide during this pandemic. Students are shifting their school to online from regular to avoid delay in studies in such uncertain times. At least they have guarantee in online education system that it wouldn't stop or paused because of this pandemic. Top government agencies, private institution and online schools have supported there learners by sharing their high quality resources free of cost online. During this closure period, online schools have proved their matter by being supportive and proactive for the need of learners.

As due to this pandemic situation majority of the classes are being taken virtually, among which there are students who are lagging behind the educational facility. There are many ways students can develop new skills and gain knowledge for free in spare time. Many universities and other educational institutions are offering free online courses, complete with tests, quizzes, reading material, study guides and even textbooks. It will not be education; it would be a ritual of learning from monitor and vomit out in another keyboard. Real education as we all know is learning the art of growing in a heterogeneous society of classmates even at 75 years of age in touch on e-mail and beneficial contacts on may issues. But as online isn't face to face, not even with webcams and microphones. That digital separation impacts social and emotional learning, communication and requires additional skill sets and technology to be a positive experience. Let alone successful, veteran teachers with exceptional classroom skills don't all have those digital skills, or perhaps just lack of experience. A teacher well mastered in using voice infection, a knowing glance and silence in the classroom can become awkward and uncomfortable with the technology standing in between them and the students. In spite of all disadvantages online education is

going to prove its durability and usefulness in coming decades by providing qualitative education.

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